

Development of a Continuous Flow Setup for the Synthesis of Ruthenium(II) Photosensitizers

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Equipment Used for the Continuous Setup

Table S1: Equipment used for the continuous flow setup.

Setup equipment	Producer	Specifications
Pumps P1,P2,P3	KNF	FEM 1.09 TT. 55 RC, KNF SIM DOS 10
2,3-path valves	Bolender	Internal thread ¼ “ UNF 28 G, for capillary OD 1/8” & ID 1/16”
Gas distributor	Bolender	Bolender 1 to 8 Mini Distributors UNF ¼" 28 G
Flangeless fittings	IDEX	UPXP-335, PEEK, ¼ - 28 G OD 1/8”, ID 1/16”
Containers	VWR	Threaded flask GL 45 100, 200, 1000, 3000 ml
HPLC bottle distributor	Bola	GL 45, 4 connection sockets
Stepper Motor VC1	Stepper online	Nema 17, planetary gearbox, 0,067° per step
Selection valve VC1	IDEX	Bulkhead 6 position, 7 port, Internal thread ¼ “ UNF 28 G, for capillary OD 1/8” & ID 1/16”
Stepper Motor Holder VC1	-	PLA 3D print
Capillary reactor Holder CR1	-	Eloxated Aluminium,
Capillary CR1 & tubing	Bolender	PFA, OD 1/8”, ID 1/16 “
Stirring Plate CR1	Heidolph	MR Hei-Connect, heated, type: 505-40000-00
Back pressure regulator PR1	IDEX	IDEX 40 psi, P-761, 100 psi, P-762, IDEX, Check Valve Inline Assembly With Fittings CV-3000
Spectrometer UV1	Avantes	AvaSpec-ULS2048
Light source UV1	Avantes	Avalight_DHc
UVV Holder	-	PLA 3D print
Fiber cable	Avantes	FC-IR008-2 or 1Cable with 8 µm Fiber, 2 or 1 m length, SMA terminations
Control system	tinkerforge	Industrial analog out 2.0, Industrial quad relay 2.1, IO-4, LCD 128/64, Master brick 3.1, Hall effect 2.0,

Experimental Setup

Figure S1 shows the synthesis section of the setup.

Figure S1: Synthesis side of laboratory setup with flow path of reaction mixture (yellow) and DMF dosage flow path (blue).

The capillary reactor (CR1) is wrapped around a aluminum capillary holding structure and immersed in a tempered 5 L glass beaker filled with silicon oil and insulated with a polyurethane layer ($d = 2$ cm). The reactor length was set to 5, 25 and 50 m, depending on the selected experimental parameters. The beaker is stirred and heated by a magnetic stirred heating plate (Heidolph MR Hei-Connect type: 505-40000-00). Temperature is measured by an inserted Pt100 sensor.

Figure S2: Analytics side of laboratory setup with reaction mixture flow path (yellow) and light beam through the optical fibers from of light source towards the spectrometer (red).

Figure S2 shows the analytics section. The reaction mixture exiting (CR1) was cooled down in a PFA capillary coil of 1 m, immersed in an ice bath to avoid thermal deformation of the UV/vis flow through cell UV1. UV1 was setup from a 3D printed, black PLA holder that attaches optical fibers (Avantes FC-IR008-2) to the capillary and a structure that provided mechanical support (white) for the optical fiber cables and valves. The in- and outlet parts of the capillary were covered with black shrinking hose to mitigate the effects of stray light on the UV/vis measurement. Check valve PR1 with replaceable backpressure cartridges (IDEX 40 psi, P-761, 100 psi, P-762, CV-3000) was used to pressurize the reactor.

Experimental Procedure

The flowrates of pumps P2 and P3 were calibrated with pure solvent DMF. After activating the power supply of the setup, a leak test was performed by pressurizing the setup with BP1 with 1 bar N₂. Leak detection spray was used to check for leakages. The synthesis flow path was then depressurized and the main flow path was set again. Temperature and stirring speed of CR1 were set. Then the UV/vis light source was switched on. For reliable UV/vis measurements the light source was warmed up at least 15 minutes before start of experimental measurements. Avasoft 8.15.0.0 and Py4mod photoreactor control software were initialized and checked for functionality. The cooler C1 was filled with ice and water.

The manufacturer's cap for DMF was replaced with an HPLC distribution cap (Bolender HPLC distributor D606-08, GL 45) in a glove box inertized with argon gas to prevent contamination of DMF with water. The cap was equipped with three 1/16" PFA tubes, flangeless fittings and shut-off valves. The DMF container was then installed in the setup. Shut-off valves were connected to the desired tubes in the setup for nitrogen flushing and DMF dosing. The 250 ml reactant containers were cleaned three times with 10 ml acetone and dried before use. Solid reagents were weighed by using a precision scale (kern ABJ220-4NM). The filled reactant containers were installed into the experimental setup and sealed.

Prior to the start of the experiments, a UV/vis reference measurement of the pure solvent DMF for each 1 L DMF bottle was performed. Therefore, the N₂ overpressure was set to 0.125 bar overpressure. The DMF container shut-off valves were opened. BP2 was adjusted for direct dosing through the UV/vis cell. VC1 was set to VP4 and the calibration function of P1 was used for dosing of DMF. Avasoft 8.15.0.0 was used to store and extract raw data. The main flow path was then restored. In addition to the reference measurement, dark spectrum measurements with closed light source shutter were performed to account for dark noise.

For the experiments, first the reactant containers were flushed with N₂ at 0.125 bar overpressure for two minutes to remove residual air. Next, VC1 was set to VP2 and VP3 for DMF dosage through P1 to the reactant containers. After DMF dosage, VC1 was set to its initial position VP1 and the shut-off valves of the DMF container were closed to prevent contamination of the DMF container. Then ST1 was started to dissolve the precursor in the reactant container. For experiments with the insoluble precursor [RuCl₂(COD)]_n, stirring was maintained throughout the entire experiment. For the soluble precursor [RuCl₂(DMSO)₄] stirring was maintained for 15 minutes until no precursor particles could be observed. The experimental procedure was continued only after complete dissolution of [RuCl₂(DMSO)₄] was reached. Due to the high solubility of tbbpy in DMF, no stirring was applied to the ligand reactant container.

The suction line, pump heads and discharge line of P2 and P3 were prefilled up to M1 using the internal fill function to ensure reliable reactant dosing. Subsequently, P2 and P3 were started to dose reactants into CR1. At the same time, UV/vis recording was started. A time delay of one residence time and a measurement interval of 30 seconds was set. During the time delay, the reactor was filled with the reaction solution. The measurements automatically started afterwards.

The setup was depressurized after the experiment and solution residues were pumped into the reactant containers. CR1 was flushed with 1 bar of N₂ to remove all reaction mixture residues.

Experimental Parameter

Synthesis experiments were performed using two different precursors $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$ and $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$. Table S2 and Table S3 show the chosen operating parameters for the experiments with the two precursors.

Table S2: Operating conditions for experiments with $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{COD})]_n$ as precursor.

Parameter	Unit	Value
ω_{ST1}	rpm	1200
ω_{CR1}	rpm	800
p_{N_2}	bar (abs)	1.125
T	°C	130-160
\dot{V}	ml min ⁻¹	4
p_{setup}	bar (abs)	1 or 4
V_{DMF}	ml	300
T	min	12.56
L_{R}	m	25
ratio ligand/precursor	mol mol ⁻¹	3:1
cooling	-	none

Table S3: Operating conditions for experiments with $[\text{RuCl}_2(\text{DMSO})_4]$ as precursor.

Parameter	Unit	Value
ω_{ST1}	rpm	1200
ω_{CR1}	rpm	800
p_{N_2}	bar (abs)	1.125

T	°C	160-190, 153
\dot{V}	ml min ⁻¹	2-32
p_{setup}	bar (abs)	6.8
V_{DMF}	ml	300, 100
τ	min	0.5-25, 45
L_R	m	5, 25, 50
ratio ligand/precursor	mol mol ⁻¹	2:1
cooling	-	ice bath

UV/Vis Analysis

Calibration

The continuous flow experiments were evaluated using absorption coefficients. The absorption coefficients were determined with an UV/vis double beam spectrophotometer (Jasco V670), equipped with a tempered cell holder (STR-773) and light source (D2/WI). A spectral resolution of 0.5 nm, a scan speed of 400 nm min⁻¹, a measurement range of 275 – 800 nm were selected. Standardized quartz glass cuvettes (d = 1 cm) were used. Table S1 summarizes determined absorption coefficients at chosen peak wavelengths of the [RuCl₂(tbbpy)₂] and Ru(tbbpy)₃ complex exemplarily.

Table S4: Selected absorption coefficients used to calculate the concentrations of the mixture composition.

Extinction coefficient / mol l ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Separate sample cuvette
$\epsilon_{\text{Ru(tbbpy)}_2\text{Cl}_2,460}$	5185
$\epsilon_{\text{Ru(tbbpy)}_3(\text{PF}_6)_2,460}$	19177
$\epsilon_{\text{Ru(tbbpy)}_2\text{Cl}_2,565}$	10991
$\epsilon_{\text{Ru(tbbpy)}_3(\text{PF}_6)_2,565}$	515

Mathematical Evaluation

The absorbance of the reaction mixture was calculated as superposition of the absorbance of the different single species present in the solution according to the Beer-Lambert law as shown in equations (1) and (2) with λ_1 and λ_2 indicate the wavelengths which were used for quantification.

$$A_{\lambda_1} = d \cdot (c_1 \cdot \epsilon_{1,\lambda_1} + c_2 \cdot \epsilon_{2,\lambda_1}) \quad (1)$$

$$A_{\lambda_2} = d \cdot (c_1 \cdot \epsilon_{1,\lambda_2} + c_2 \cdot \epsilon_{2,\lambda_2}) \quad (2)$$

With these equations, the concentrations of two absorbing species were calculated according to equations (3) and (4).

$$c_1 = \frac{A_{\lambda_1}}{d \cdot \epsilon_{1,\lambda_1}} - c_2 \cdot \frac{\epsilon_{2,\lambda_1}}{\epsilon_{1,\lambda_1}} \quad (3)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{\left(A_{\lambda_2} - \frac{A_{\lambda_1} \cdot \epsilon_{1,\lambda_2}}{\epsilon_{1,\lambda_1}} \right)}{\left(\epsilon_{2,\lambda_2} - \frac{\epsilon_{2,\lambda_1} \cdot \epsilon_{1,\lambda_2}}{\epsilon_{1,\lambda_1}} \right)} \quad (4)$$